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NATIONAL CONFERENCE

Vidyalankar Institute of Technology

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**National Conference
on**

"Innovations in Electronics & Information Technology"

This is to certify that

a paper titled

**"Rapid Prototyping Technology (RPT)-
Process Techniques and Applications"**

authored by **Jayen Modi**

has been published in the Proceedings of the National Conference,
"Innovations in Electronics & Information Technology" organized by
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Prof. Shrikant Velankar
Convener, IEIT 2009

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